

SYNTHESIS OF $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}/\text{Ag}$ COMPOSITE SUPERCONDUCTORS BY A CITRIC ACID SOL-GEL METHOD

A.L. Juwono¹, S. Waluyo², and S. Poertadji¹

¹ *Department of Physics, Faculty of Mathematics and Sciences,
University of Indonesia, Depok, 16424, Indonesia*

² *Present address: PT Iron Hill Mitra Sejati Microelectronic Packaging,
Tangerang, Indonesia*

SUMMARY: $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ superconductor and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}/\text{Ag}$ composite superconductors were synthesized by a citric acid sol-gel method. The weight ratios of silver to $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ were varied by 5 %, 10 % and 15 %. Superconducting phenomenon was observed on $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ superconductor, and on 5 and 10 weight % Ag composites. X-ray diffraction patterns of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x} / \text{Ag}$ have been analysed by Powder Diffraction Package (PDP) simulation and indicated that all specimens contained $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ crystal. Critical current densities (J_c) of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x} / \text{Ag}$ were obtained at 77 K using four-point-probe method (I-V Curve Technique). Silver additions of up to 10 % weight increased the critical current density values and improved the degree of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ crystallization. The presence of large amount of silver degraded the superconducting property and decreased the critical current density.

KEYWORDS: YBCO, YBCO/Ag, citric acid, Powder Diffraction Package, critical current, Meissner effect

INTRODUCTION

Superconductors became important electronic materials after H.K. Onnes in 1911 found a zero resistance of mercury at a critical temperature (T_c) of 4.2 K. After a long period of research, T_c could be raised until 23.2 K for Nb_3Ge superconductors [1]. An interesting invention, that was found by G. Bednorz and K.A. Miller in 1986, was a ceramic oxide based superconductor, $\text{La}_{5-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{Cu}_5\text{O}_{5(3-y)}$ with T_c of 30 K [2]. This material was called a high temperature superconductor. Some modifications have been worked to obtain higher critical temperature materials, such as to substitute La atoms to Y atoms to produce $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ (YBCO) system [3]. The highest T_c (220 K) was found by J.T. Chen in 1989 for $\text{Y}_5\text{Ba}_6\text{Cu}_{11}\text{O}_{7-x}$ system [4]. The bulk YBCO superconducting materials have low strength, low modulus and low strain to failure. Other important variables of superconducting phenomenon, beside critical temperature (T_c), are critical magnetic field (H_c) and critical current density (J_c). The main problem is how to produce a material in the superconducting state with T_c , H_c and J_c are as high as possible. To enhance the mechanical properties, T_c , and J_c , some additives, such as silver, silver oxide, zirconia, stainless steel fibres, were added to the material [5].

YBCO system has an orthorhombic perovskite structure as shown in Figure 1 [6]. Difficulty in manufacturing single phase crystal YBCO system has been an interested issue. It has been reported that there are three different techniques in producing superconductors, namely the solid state reaction, the diffusion and the solution reaction. The solution reaction method employs cheaper base materials, processes in lower sintering temperatures and produces more homogeneous system materials in large scale compare to the others two method.

Fig. 1: Orthorhombic perovskite structure of a $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ crystal [6]

The aims of this research were examining the synthesis of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$ composite superconductors using a citric acid sol-gel method and observing silver addition to superconducting properties (including T_c , H_c , J_c).

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and Equipment

Both $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ superconductor and $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$ composite superconductors were produced by the solution reaction, namely a citric acid sol-gel method. The weight ratios of silver to $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ were varied by 5 %, 10 % and 15 %. Three samples were prepared for each type of specimen. Basic materials for the synthesis had purity of about 99 %.

The synthesis procedure can be seen in Figure 2. The sol solution was synthesized on a magnetic plate equipped with a magnetic stirrer. While the gel solution was produced in a vacuum evaporation type JEE-4X. Calcination and sintering were proceed in a controlled furnace with temperature range from room up to 1000°C. Pellet shaped specimens were pressed using a hydraulic pressure which had 150 kN maximum power force.

Fig. 2: The synthesis procedure of YBa₂Cu₃O_{7-x}/Ag composite superconductors by a citric acid sol-gel method

Meissner Effect Test

A permanent magnetic of SmCo was used for Meissner effect tests at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K).

Critical Current Density (J_c) Measurement

A linear four point probe was used for this test. During measurement, the specimens were immersed in liquid nitrogen (77 K). A current-voltage curve was obtained from this work. When the voltage changes from zero to a certain finite value, the current obtained is the critical one.

X-ray Diffraction

A Phillip PW 3710 diffractometer was used to obtain X-ray diffraction patterns. The X-ray source was CoK_{α} and the diffraction angle was between 20° up to 80° . Powder Diffraction Package (PDP) simulation was applied to analyse the experimental results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 3 and 4 are X-ray diffraction patterns of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ superconductor and $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$ composite superconductors respectively. Perovskite phase of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ was proved by the highest peak at 38° at both Figures 3a and 4a. Comparing these figures, silver additions increased the intensity of the 38° peak. It means that silver additions improved the degree of crystallinity. These patterns were compared to previous study and gave similar results [7]. There are three other peaks at 45° , 52° and 77° at Figure 4a. These peaks exposed the presence of silver phase in the specimens. This pattern was confirmed by PDP simulation. A detail study showed that as the silver content increased, these three peaks increased accordingly. Thus, simulation showed evidently that the presence of silver phase in the bulk material built a YBCO/Ag system composite superconductor. It was shown that the silver phase did not interfere the perovskite YBCO crystal. Hence, the silver phase filled the void positions between crystal grains and could increase the mass and the current density.

Critical current densities of both $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ and $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$ were graphed to weight % Ag as shown in Figure 5. The composite containing 5 and 10 % Ag had higher J_c than the pure YBCO superconductor. In contrast, the J_c value of composite containing 15 % Ag was zero. This deviation was confirmed by Meissner effect test. The superconductor and the composite containing 5 and 10 % Ag exhibited the Meissner effect, while the composite containing 15 % Ag did not demonstrate that one.

Silver additions of up to 10 % weight increased the YBCO grain percentage (this was proved by XRD pattern) and might increase the YBCO grain size [8]. This state resulted decreasing the void fractions. Therefore, the J_c values of the composite superconductors were higher than that of pure superconductor itself. The percentage of YBCO crystal decreased by addition of 15 % weight of Ag and degraded superconducting properties.

Fig. 3a: X-ray diffraction pattern of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$

Fig. 3b: PDP simulation of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$

Fig. 4a: X-ray diffraction pattern of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/10\% Ag$

Fig. 4b: PDP simulation of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/10\% Ag$

Fig. 5: Graph of critical current densities (J_c) versus weight % Ag of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ and $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$

CONCLUSIONS

$YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ superconductors and $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/Ag$ composite superconductors have been synthesized by a solution technique, namely a citric acid sol-gel method. The best composition was the $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}/10\%$ Ag which shown the highest J_c . Silver additions of up to 10 % weight increased the critical current density values and improved the degree of $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ crystallization. The presence of large amount of silver degraded the superconducting property and decreased the critical current density.

REFERENCES

1. Kittel, C., "Introduction To Solid State Physics", 6th.ed., John Willey & Sons Inc., New York, 1991.
2. Bednorz, J.G. and K.A. Muller, Z. Phys. B 64, 1989, p. 189.
3. Wu, M.K., Ashburn, J.R., Torng, C.J., Hor, P.H., Meng, R.L., Go, L., Huang, Z.J., Wang, Y.O., and Wu, C.W., Physical Review Letters, Vol. 58, 1987, p 908.
4. Chen, J.T., Qian, L.X., Wang, L.Q., Wenger, L.E., and Logothetis, E.M., Modern Physics Letters B3, 1989, pp 1197 - 1206.
5. Vipulandan, C. and S. Salib, Journal of Material Science. Vol. 30, 1995, pp 763 - 769.
6. Grant, P.M., Beyers, R.B., Engler, E.M., Lim, G., Parkin, S.S.P., Ramirez, M.L., Lee, V.Y., Nazzal, A., Vazquez, J.E., and Savoy, R.J., Physical Review B 35, No. 13, 1987, p 7242.
7. Jiaju, D., Jianyi, J, Xiang, W., and Huaqing, Y., Chinese Physics, Vol. 9, No. 4, 1988, pp. 1011 - 1014.
8. Dwir, B., Appl. Phys. Lett. Vol. 55 (4), 1989, p 399.